

The affective economies of private renting in the Majority World

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[please do not quote as this is work in progress at a fairly initial stage]

The interest in the private renting sector as a mechanism generator of new inequalities has been uncomfortably dominated by Anglo-Saxon accounts. In these countries, given their better institutionalised regulatory, welfare and tenant-activism regimes, much of the focus has fallen on economic and policy studies to propose ways to increase the sector's efficiency and address precarity. But what about the Majority World?

For instance, in Ghana, landlords' requirements for a two to five years advanced rent has persisted for decades (Arku et al. 2012). Jumping continents to India, insecure property rights tie both tenants and landlords into risky arrangements (Naik 2015). Bouncing west to Brazil favelas (Lonardoni and Bolay 2016), positive synergies are created between employment-included tenants/lodgers and employment-excluded landlords. Closer to the Minority World but in many ways subaltern, access to subsidised energy price in Romania was initially tied in December 2022 to one's first residence, turning for once the attention to the estimated one million renters who could not benefit as landlords prefer to control utility contracts (Serban 2022). Far from dismissing the plight of private tenants in the over-studied Anglo-Saxon countries and other jurisdictions of the Minority World (Gustafsson et al. 2019; Soaita et al. 2020), practices as exemplified above stem from and construct completely different and far more precarious political and 'affective regimes' (Anderson 2014) in the tenant/landlord relationship.

Following Kumar's (1996, 2016) renewed call to start understanding the renting arrangements in the Majority World away of theories born from the realities and aspirations of the Minority World, this presentation presents a Critical Interpretative Synthesis of the academic literature (77 studies were identified for reviewing and 65 to contextualize findings). The ongoing analysis pays attention to the ways by which the economies and politics of private renting are assembled through a multiplicity of social relations between actors (tenants, landlords, their families, employes, communities, authorities), materialities (money, houses, infrastructure, geology and landscape), cultural norms, regulatory and ideological landscapes which form diverse regimes of affect, power, risk and trust flowing through any and every tenant-landlord relationship, often simultaneously making and unmaking 'home' be it materially or socially, in the real or the imaginary. It is hope that findings will enrich our theoretical lenses in understanding the social universe of private renting.

Keywords: systematic review; Majority World; tenant-landlord relationship; affective regimes.

1. Introduction

1.1. The AFFECTIVE-PRS project

The 2008 Global Financial Crisis and the Covid-19 pandemic have exposed rental housing as a mechanism that generates important inequalities of wealth, health and wellbeing in much of the world, while failing to give many tenants a ‘home’. Academic interest in the Anglo-Saxon and the old EU member states has recently contributed disturbing insights (e.g. poor housing quality, insecurity, eviction, economic stress), raising legitimate concerns about tenants’ wellbeing in the more hidden, hence riskier private renting sectors (PRS) where informal transactions increase risks and hide vulnerability away from state regulatory gaze.

Sharing these important concerns, AFFECTIVE-PRS project engages with the affective economies of emerging, ‘hidden’ PRS, taking as a case-study the post-communist space, specifically Romania. It aims to: **Understand** a hidden social world, by asking why tenants and landlords engage in the sector, whether their practices permit making a private tenancy home, and how they construct ideas of power, risk and trust; **Advance** theory by conceiving home as an assemblage of materials, money, relations and affects; **Inform** the national and international debate on PRS regulation.

Methodologically, this project will develop a synthesis of the international literature of the ‘Majority World’ (i.e. this exclude the developed Anglophone and Western Europe countries), which is the focus of this paper; will approach tenants and landlords in Romania through an online qualitative questionnaire, which allows them to freely and fully describe their experiences; photo-elicitation interviews with Romanian tenants and landlords to obtain deeper insights; and a co-production workshop with policy, practice and academia in order to imagine a sustainable and fair PRS in Romania and inform the national debate on its regulation.

As the PRS generates important inequalities of wealth and wellbeing, it is important to maximize the project impact. Academic impact will be attained through publications and dissemination through conferences, seminars and workshops. Findings will be communicated to the general public through briefing papers, blogs, media articles and a “Guide for Good Practice” as well as through interactive digital platforms. By helping **construct a shared understanding of good practice** in the PRS, the project could theoretically improve the lives of many private tenants, whether it be the officially registered 252,000 or the over one million estimated.

1.2. The aim of this paper

This paper reports work in progress and draws on a Critical Interpretative Synthesis (CIS) as an approach to reviewing systematically the literature (Depraetere et al. 2020). Briefly, CIS is ‘*a methodology that enables synthesis of large amounts of diverse qualitative data and facilitates critical engagement with the assumptions that shape and inform a body of research*’ (Farias and Laliberte Rudman 2016). Looking internationally across countries with very different arrangements of private renting, and very different political, socioeconomic and welfare contexts, this CIS addresses the international component of Objective One of the AFFECTIVE-PRS project – that is understanding tenants’ and landlords’ motivations and practices beyond the over-studied Anglo-Saxon and Western Europe states. The specific research questions which CIS hopes to address is:

- What dominant ‘structures of feeling’ (Anderson 2014) could be encountered across the affective economies of private renting in different contexts, and what make them differ from context to context?

To construct the database for reviewing, this CIS builds on a more feasible approach (Soaita et al. 2021; Soaita et al. 2019), which is described in the method section.

2. Theoretical background

There is a long debate in housing studies related to the big epistemological and ontological questions raised by cross-country comparative work, and the level of mobilization to which it may be said to have theoretical validity (e.g. for generalization; middle-range theorizing; restricted to localized, rich descriptions). Nonetheless, work at the global level has regain momentum, whether in empirically and theoretically rich mosaic-like collections (Lancione and McFarlane 2021; Powell and Simone 2022), or systematic approaches to examine and answer more precise policy-relevant housing questions (Kholodilin 2020; Soaita and Dewilde 2019).

To look across a global literature, this paper’s theoretical lenses are theories of affect which posit affective everyday life as a medium through which forms of power work. At such, affect is not just an individual emotion but rather collective registers – ‘pre-individual intensities’ or ‘structure of feeling’ (Anderson 2014, p11) - mediated through ‘soft’ forms of power (e.g. discourse, morality and other social and cultural norms), emergent from specific material arrangements, mobilized in the political game, infusing institutions and generating action (Akerlof and Shiller 2009). The fact that economies of all kind, and housing economies in particular are geared by affect is a long standing argument. In this section I only wish to name the most prominent affective registers of the economies of private renting markets:

- Greed*: Karl Marx's (in Anderson 2014 p.9) insisted that the affective regime of greed and lack of care of capital lead to the exploitation of labour, posing the 'housing question' (Engels 1872) of early industrialization, and some argue of today (Aalbers and Christophers 2014). Adam Smith celebrated the law of self-interest that make markets work (Wells 2013). Likewise, the affective register of greed can be recognized in the pursue of dizzily quick profits by large corporate players of 'capitalism 3.0' through the assetisation of everyday life (Christophers 2022; Christophers 2023). According to this perspective, landlords' and tenants' interests are to be thought as being in unresolved, tense opposition. The extent of landlords' greed - and tenants' exploitation and lived everyday forms of (financial, physical, or symbolic slow or eventual) *violence* – is generally thought of being structured by the supply/demand rapport in the market, which is relationally produced by many political actors, most powerfully by the state (Bourdieu 2005).
- Care*: the fact that other economies exist outside or alongside capitalist economic practices became the central tenet of the 'diverse economies' theoretical framework (Gibson-Graham 2014; Gibson-Graham and Dombroski 2020). While it was recognized that not all other-than-capitalist economic practices were developed outside the structure of greed and self-interest (e.g. economies of corruption, bribery, mafia-like networks), many others are centered on care. Care provision can be given at different distances away from the market, those of: the gendered (intergenerational) family; local communities (the church, the volunteering sector); and the state. Care practices distributed outside the market were conceptualized as decommodification while those offered in conjunction with markets as partial decommodification (Esping-Andersen 1990). Esping-Andersen, and others who expanded his theory, showed that, across country-regimes, care was primarily distributed by the market (neoliberal regimes), the corporate (corporatist regimes), the family (familistic regimes) and the welfare or developmental state. According to this perspective, rented housing could be fully decommodified when the state and other non-profit organisations engage in landlordism, offering affordable housing as a care/social right; partially decommodified through state rent benefit or rent control, and family rent-free living; but even when fully commodified, it was shown that many individual landlords were not powered by greed, but by insuring their family wellbeing through property ownership and renting income (Soaita et al. 2016), particularly in the context of weathering down of the welfare state. Under the structure of care, the market tenant/landlord relationship could be theoretically conceived as one of mutual rather than self-interest (Power and Mee 2020).

- *Cruel optimism*: coined by Berlant (2011), the concept centers on an object's double-banded promises of flourishing and harming, and the blurring boundaries between these states in the struggle of pursuing it as a lifestyle desire (Anderson et al. 2023). Simply put, a "relation of cruel optimism exists when something you desire is actually an obstacle to your flourishing (Berlant, 2011, p. 1). Homeownership as an object of desire infuses many cultures, even in renting societies such as Sweden and Germany. However, the more it attracts the imagination of less affluent people, the more it becomes a cruel fantasy, an obstacle to flourish, driving feelings of frustration, the struggle of over-saving when renting (McKee et al. 2020), the anxiety of being unable to support long-term commitment or stretching debt over decades or even two-generations (Langley 2008; McCormack 2012).

As Anderson (2014) emphasized, a structure of feeling contains multiple emotions, affects and ambivalences. For instance, *greed* may associate avarice and excess, longing, selfishness, craving; *care* may implicate love and hate, normative sentimentality, anxiety, suspicion; *cruel optimism* may involve hope and disappointment, frustration, melancholia, craving, and avarice. Structures of feelings are mediated relationally through materialities (e.g. specific atmospheres), cultural discourses (of must-have wants turned into needs) and mobilized in ideological struggle.

To be continued and refined.

3. Method

The protocol of locating the relevant literature to be reviewed in this study and the operationalization of the 'Majority World' (Simone and Fauzan 2013) was described in detail in Soaita (2023). Chiefly, I looked for qualitative literature¹ that reports the experiences of tenants and landlords² involved in the field of housing.³

The Anglo-Saxon countries, the old members and associates of the EU/EEA and a few developed other countries (Canada, Japan) were excluded as representing the 'Minority World'.⁴ This is not to say that hidden, informal renting arrangements are non-existent in these countries but they are numerically marginal (Morris et al. 2021). Given the very uneven countries' representation, a

¹ String: "qualitative OR interview OR ethnograph* OR "case study" OR "case studies"

² String: (private AND (tenant* OR renter*)) OR lodger* OR squatter* OR flatmate* OR (HMO* AND resident*) OR (HMO* AND tenant*) OR (private AND landlord*) OR (tenant* AND landlord*) OR (landlord*-tenant* OR tenant*-landlord*)

³ String: (housing OR home OR house OR flat OR apartment OR flat-share OR (hous* AND "in multiple occupation") OR (rooming AND hous*) OR (boarding AND hous*) OR (Rooming AND hous*))

⁴ Excluded countries (in three-letter acronym): AUS, AUT, BEL, CAN, CHE, DEU, DNK, ELA, ESP, FIN, FRA, GBR, GRC, IRL, ITA, ISL, JPN, LIE, LUX, MLT, NLD, NOR, NZL, PRT, SWE, USA.

decision was made to include all countries notwithstanding their significantly different context of renting. For a similar approach see Kholodilin (2020).

Table 1 summarises the process, showing the steps, the action, the number of references at the end of each action, and explanatory notes while Figure 1 shows the geographical distribution of the studies to be reviewed. Given the extraordinary geographical spread of the literature, and the related very different historical and current institutional contexts, 65 more references were put aside to be consulted when/if needed (besides the 77 references to be reviewed).

As this is work in-progress, for the purpose of this paper, two contrasting case-studies are chosen for discussion: the post-communist space of Eastern Europe (8 papers) and Ghana (10 papers; the most represented country in the sample); in addition, for quantitative or policy context, 5 and 2 more papers were read for Eastern Europe and Ghana, respectively.

Table 1 Summary of the process

Steps	Action	No.	Explanatory notes
S1	Preliminary steps		Setting the parameters of the systematic searches (e.g. choice of databases, searching fields, type of reference, discipline, publishing timeline, geography). Piloting of the searching strings, independently and together, was essential for good calibration.
S2	Retrieved	154	Systematic searches were performed in SCOPUS and Web of Science on 10 Jan 2023. In total, 154 references were exported in an EndNote database.
S3	Unique references	120	Following EndNote automatic removal of duplicates, a total of 120 unique references remained (101 journal articles; 11 books; 8 book chapters).
S4	Manual check for criteria fit (in titles, abstracts and full text)	30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 89 references were excluded for language misfit (n=1), could not be accessed (n=6), were previously unrecognised duplicates (n=7), country misfit (n=13) and thematic misfit (n=63). See Box 1. • 30 references were retained: 29 articles; 1 book chapter, 1 book (26% relevant hits of the total retrieved).
S5*	Boosting the sample with manual searches	67	<p>37 new references were added. Searches/inquiries were performed in the order below (17-20 Jan 2023):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 8 additional references were identified in Housing Studies, out of the first most-relevant 300 publications; keyword: “renting”, which also returned “rented, rental or rent” (3.0% relevant hits of the total)

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 additional references were identified in the International Journal of Housing Policy, out of the first most-relevant 300 publications; keyword: “renting”, which also returned “rented, rental or rent” (1.0% relevant hits of the total). • 3 additional references were identified in Geoforum, out of the first most-relevant 400 publications; separate searches with the keywords: “renting” and “housing”; (0.8% relevant hits of the total). • 13 additional references were identified in Habitat International, out of the first most-relevant 300 publications; keyword: “renting” (4.3% relevant hits of the total). • 7 additional references were identified in Urban Studies, out of the first most-relevant 300 publications (searches for “renting”; 2.3% relevant hits of the total) • 3 additional references were identified in Google Scholar, out of the first 300 publications (searches for “renting”; 1.0% relevant hits of the total) •
		77	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10 new references were added sourced from the references of the 66 above identified papers (n=8) or recommended by academic experts (n=2)

Early draft

Figure 1 The geographical distribution of the papers to be reviewed

Source: By the author

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4. Discussion

4.1. Eastern Europe

Even though only studies that included a qualitative research element were reviewed, some of those reporting on Eastern Europe gave little qualitative flavor of the lived experience of landlords and tenants, or their social relationship (Erdősi et al. 2000; Hegedüs et al. 2014; Lux and Mikeszova 2012; Sendi and Mali 2015). These studies tended to report on the constitution of private rental arrangements across all socioeconomic groups and urban geographies. Inferring from these analyses, it could be said that *care* as a structure of feeling based on recognized mutual interest best describe the affective economies of renting not least because both landlords and tenants are on average relatively well-off.

Care is however mediated by different actors and institutions, and produced differentiated outcomes across different segments of the market. Looking at landlords⁵ in Slovenia's fully liberalized private rental markets (Sendi and Mali 2015), individual landlords, who dominate the market, are reported to rent out well-maintained and well-furnished properties (about 90% of all rentals); make use of rental contracts and allow rent payment through bank transfers (89% of all landlords); allow registration of residence if requested (81% of all landlords) while rents remain at affordable levels (on average 30% of tenant income). In the absence of state regulation, a *caring market* seems to have developed in Slovenia, shaped by a balanced supply/demand report and by a more equal society. The authors thought their findings to be quite surprising given the dominant public discourse of landlords being powered by greed and exclusive self-interest.

Interestingly, a regime of very '*distorted*' *care* (i.e. highly biased/unequal) can also infuse the affective economies of renting in systems dominated by lack of trust, as reported in Hungary (Erdősi et al. 2000; Hegedüs et al. 2014). Looking through the prism of experts, Hegedüs et al. (2014) convincingly argued that legal uncertainties and an uneasy mix of relatively strong tenant protection from eviction (e.g. disallowed in winter notwithstanding the ground), under-regulation and non-enforceability of contracts breaches (i.e. non-payment of rent or anti-social behavior) has resulted in blatant tenant discrimination in the market. On the one hand, tenants who come recommended by one's social network or enjoy good educational and socioeconomic capital are positively discriminated, including being offered below-market rent. On the other hand, low-income groups and certain ethnicities (mostly Roma people but also Middle-East and Asian migrants) are

⁵ This was a non-participant, qualitative covert research with 150 properties advertised for renting being each visited by 2 hired students.

refused entry or filtered out by high advertised rents (negotiated down in the case of favorite applicants). A regime of distrust means that the sector remains small, without being able to capture the high share of the vacant stock, and leaving few options for the poorest and Roma people, who are so pushed in an even more hidden subsector reigned by the exploitation of the ‘under-class’ (Ladányi 2016).

Indeed, disturbing evidence on the affective economies of *greed and exploitation* structuring the disadvantaged bottom segment of the renting sector comes from the Czech Republic (Kupka et al. 2021; Walach et al. 2021) and Romania (Lancione 2019), with a focus on the advanced marginality of Roma people.

The case of the Czech Republic is particularly interesting in its singularity: an unusually strong welfare system offering various forms of support (rent assistance, unemployment benefits, child support) resulted in the so-called ‘poverty business’ practiced by slum landlords exploiting the socially-assisted Roma population. The fact that the welfare policies of the state produced economies of *greed and exploitation* can be explained by qualifications. Relatively generous welfare assistance came conditioned with more trust being offered to landlords than tenants (e.g. we learn that for a tenant to be able to move it is the landlord who must confirm there was no rent unpaid or property damaged). The oppressive consequences of conditionality in welfare distribution were well documented in the UK’s policies of austerity (Atkinson et al. 2012; Blyth 2012; McKenzie 2015). The structure of feeling infusing the Czech welfare state can so be qualified as *suspicious care*. It seems nonetheless puzzling that, under the certainty of rent being paid by the state, the main rental system has not opened its doors to welfare-assisted applicants – which shows the extend of (historic) ethnic discrimination in the Czech society, and related ethnicisation of poverty.

The two reviewed studies report stark exploitative and abusive practices of: overcharging rent and many other payments (e.g. for visitors, use of washing machine, fridge, TV, hot shower, access to shared kitchen or even furniture deemed to be rented from the landlord) in substandard housing, often deemed unfit for living; using abusive contracts (e.g. tenants forced to declare the accommodation being in good condition, then exploited into captivity as they can simply no longer leave without paying for fictitious ‘property damage’); massive disinvestment; exposure to coercion and violence, even forced to exert them against their own peers; physical violence and threats, including that of eviction.

If it can be argued that the Czech welfare state provided care, albeit *suspicious care* towards the most disadvantaged in society, the neoliberal Romanian state endorsed a true regime of *greed and exploitation* by allowing the restitution of rented property to prior owners or their heirs with tenant protection limited to 5 years only. Romania displays a classic example of capitalist accumulation by the dispossession of the poorest (Harvey 2005), justified under a specific postcommunist moral frame of historic justice through the restitution of confiscated/nationalized property to prior owners (Lancione 2019), to be later passed away into the hands of financialised corporations, not unlike in the Czech Republic (Lux and Mikeszova 2012), Poland (Łuczak and Ławrynowicz 2021) or Hungary (Erdősi et al. 2000). Lancione's (2019) excels in its "*trying to connect larger political-economic trends to everyday urban lives, relating infrastructures, atmospheres, and flows to the micropolitics of the social field*". The context of the story is succinctly exposed and relevant beyond the Romanian case-study:

[they were] paying rent to the State for more than 30 years. When the building was restituted to its pre-nationalisation owner in 2002, the people signed contracts with the new owner, who subsequently sold the property to a Norwegian investor in 2007. In September 2014, this investor decided to not renew their tenancies, and proceeded to evict the community

The paper focuses on the Roma peoples' acts of resistance post-eviction, initial state inaction turning into policies/politics of invisibility (removing the people away of the public gaze without offering solutions or alternatives). Properties changing hands through state restitution to prior owners or their heirs and further to financialised (global) investors, as reported by Lancione, occurred across Eastern Europe, particularly in prime locations. Kusiak (2019) referred to such processes as 'primitive accumulation' through 'legal robbery' mediated by the state in most EE countries and exceptionally by neoliberal-minded Courts in Poland where no national policies existed. Focusing on older women navigating such historic transformations, Łuczak and Ławrynowicz (2021) give voice to Bożena's emotions:

But why am I actually talking about it? I am talking about this because it hurts me very much up to today. I cannot deal with it. And the building was, as I said, privatized in 1995. My husband had passed away, and they took these dwellings from us. We became Someone's purchase. We did not learn that we had been sold until two years after it had happened.

Implicitly or explicitly, some of the reviewed studies (Kupka et al. 2021; Lancione 2019; Łuczak and Ławrynowicz 2021) substantiate relations of *cruel optimism*. In the hope of receiving allocation to social housing against all odds, numerically (just 1% of the housing stock) and symbolically (the Roma population being stigmatized as undeserving poor), the evicted protesters endured months of

inhabiting the street in front of their lost homes in the rainy days of autumn and the cold days of winter, with not even basic facilities provided. Given the little odds they had to obtain resolution, I read this structure of feeling as *hopeless optimism* (conceptualized elsewhere as *waithood* that is the social negation of hope).

However, a relation of cruel optimism could not be formed, Berlant (2011) argued, unless the tantalizing hope is not maintain through the experience of others. Resolution could occur quite suddenly, as Łuczak and Ławrynowicz (2021) reported the happy outcome for Zuzanna of being saved from the precarity of renting privately by the municipality:

Suddenly in February, I received a phone call. Somebody telephoned me from City Hall and told me that I was supposed to report to the Dwelling Affairs Department. I wasn't informed that I got a dwelling, but that I was to present myself. I didn't even ask if it was about a dwelling, I simply went. I found out that there was a dwelling available because somebody had resigned, and I could get it. I had to decide, and so I did. And here I am.

While social housing is an object of desire for many low-income people, most renters are clearly attached to the socially-constructed idea of owning their owned home. As Erdösi et al (2000) showed, over 80% of private renters aspired to become homeowners in 5 years' time in Hungary. While homeownership may be certainly achieved by affluent renters and those enjoying family support, it is clear – though not substantiated in the reviewed literature – that many would struggle. Striving for homeownership at any cost (e.g. severe saving, giving up on what is imagined as the 'good life') and in the current context of high mortgage rates and inflation, clearly posits homeownership as an object of cruel optimism for many. But nowhere perhaps is attachment to homeownership a clearer case of cruel optimism than in the case of Ghana, to which I now turn.

4.2. Ghana

It remains unclear why Ghana is the most represented country in my sample (e.g. university power? my own biased curiosity?) but its (historic) system of 2-to-5 years advanced rent is striking, albeit not unique as it can also be found in, e.g. Nigeria, Tanzania and Kenya (Adu-Gyamfi et al. 2020; Arku et al. 2012). Ghana shows a strong first-generation rent control regime (Malpezzi et al. 1990): fixed rents, updated irregularly by the Government, are further eroded by decades of high inflation. However, a context of massive housing shortages in any tenure, posits a vicious cocktail for tenants' *economic exploitation and symbolic and physical violence* as they commonly live side-by-side to their landlords/landladies in the traditional compound house (Asante and Ehwi 2022; Eduful and Hooper 2019).

In my reading of this literature, physical proximity between tenants and landlords does not seem to spur the formation of social capital, community of interest or caring (informal) markets but relations of control and asymmetric power not unlike those reported in relation to lodgers and their in-house landlords or in the rooming houses of Australia or Canada (Soaita 2021; Soaita et al. 2020). Rent control and very poor housing quality may have made renting ‘affordable’ to the majority of urban poor (of up to 10% of household income is mentioned, e.g. Malpezzi et al. 1990), but procuring the 2-to-5 advanced rent required to access a tenancy remains a struggle; many need to borrow from family and friends, from Ghana or abroad. Once in a tenancy, the oppressive shadow of the advanced rent does not fade away as saving for the next one (and for returning the debt incurred) kicks in. To exemplify:

If you live in a house that the homeowner relies solely on the rent for his livelihood, then you will have no peace of mind in the house when your rent advance is due and you have to renew. The landlord can come to your door and knock to remind you that you have to pay another advance or move out for another person to rent the room. At that time, the landlord might have already made a list of expenditure that he will use the rent advance for. But it is not easy paying for rent advance to cover three years or even five years (Adu-Gyamfi et al. 2020)

Don't want to think about my next advance rent because it is quite soul destroying ... It is a stressful thought and it always gives me headache... It makes me really sick, and I have no idea what I will do...(Luginaah et al. 2010)

There are pertinent economic explanations for the widespread practice of long-term advanced rent, despite legal stipulations capping it at 6, exceptionally 12 months (Asante and Ehwi 2022; Malpezzi et al. 1990). For instance, it is rational for landlords to try to maximize their profit by demanding the rent in advance, given that rent control (state's *care policy* of partial decommodification) as well as high inflation make rents uneconomically small. In the absence of construction loans, landlords need the advance rent to expand their portfolios by adding rooms to their compound houses or building new houses and thereby helping tackle the huge housing shortages – while consolidating their position in the propertied class. Landlords are usually less skilled and less employable than their tenants, hence their livelihoods depend on advanced rent. Advanced rent prevents tenants defaulting on rents. Research with landlords show these rationalities to be firmly grounded in landlords' discourses of justification. To exemplify (both quotes in Arku et al. 2012):

It allowed me to complete my compound house. Once I managed to finish a couple of rooms, and got lump sum of money from the tenant, I used that money to complete another two rooms. I am starting to put up another property at Hatso.

I earn my living from the rent I collect from tenants. If prices of goods are increasing, I don't have a choice because I also buy from the very same market as everyone else. Like any other responsible parent, I also worry about the welfare of my children who need to be fed and go to school.

Conversely, tenants find the mechanism of long-term advanced rent as “*‘unlawful’, ‘greedy’, ‘abusive’, ‘injustice’, ‘fraudulent’ and ‘unfair’*”, generating frustration and feelings of helplessness (Arku et al. 2012). Such descriptors are the epitomes of *affective economies of greed*. Landlords' economic power and tenants' captivity (through the advance rent but also through supply pressure) spur further practices of symbolic violence: threat of eviction or rent increase; spying, harassment and intrusion; demand of unpaid DIY, which all were shown to directly affect tenants' physical and mental health (Luginaah et al. 2010).

The wicked financial, symbolic and physical treatment that tenants widely report means that many would agree that “*Home for me is like a living in hell and I have no emotional attachment there*” (Luginaah et al. 2010). Such experiences set instead the desire to own, and at such open up a context of cruel optimism through the attachment to the self-built home in a country where homeownership is highly selective as three quarter of all the population is renting, and half of the population was classed as low and lower-income households:

The brighter side is that the pressure and bad treatments that we receive from the homeowners is a motivating factor for building our own houses. Probably, if not for them, many low-income earners like myself would not have made the attempt at homeownership (Adu-Gyamfi et al. 2020).

Asante et al (2018) bring testimony that building while renting is “*‘stressful’, ‘tough’ and ‘a nightmare’*”. Some participants said “*you cannot live proper life. You are always thinking of what to do*”. Cruel sacrifices in the struggle to own abound: living apart of one's family while acting as a caretaker of other peoples' unfinished houses in order to save (Gough and Yankson 2011); giving up on any modest form of leisure, holidaying or entertainment; developing a culture of thrift; cutting off extended family obligations; even neglecting children's needs. Attachment to homeownership as a safe home can be nonetheless achieved by some at the end of a long and winding road of hope:

I am currently struggling to combine renting and self-building a house. My rent is due by the end of this year (that is, in 7 months' time) and need to finish my own building quickly to avoid paying another 2 years of rent advance. I have decided to commit 90 percent of my salary into building my house (Asante et al. 2018).

5. Conclusions

This paper sets itself a challenging goal: to look across the international literature in order to extract insights on the affective economies of private renting in countries that cannot be more different.

Drawing on theories of affect, the discussion aimed to delineate the dominant structures of feeling that could be encountered across the affective economies of private renting in different contexts, and what make such structures different from context to context. As this is early work-in-progress, the discussion focused on Eastern Europe (based on 8 papers) and Ghana (based on 13 papers).

Rooted on different theoretical frameworks, I substantiated the structures of feeling of greed/exploitation, that of care and that of cruel optimism. I found a dominant structure of *care centered on mutual market interest* in the well-functioning albeit small private renting sector of Slovenia. I believe that it was comparable economic affluence between landlords and tenants in a more equal society and a balanced supply/demand rapport that made this possible. Hungary's regime of distrust produced a market system of *distorted care* that is positive discrimination for some people at the cost of negative discrimination and exclusion of others. This structure of feeling of distorted care, I suspect, is no different than the situation in Romania, where I have already collected some qualitative data supporting this view. I have also discussed the structure of *suspicious care* given by the Czech welfare state, which twined with widespread ethnic stigmatization, has generated abject tenants' exploitation through the so-called 'poverty business' targeting socially-assisted Roma people. While there may be hope to adjust policy detail in the case of the Czech Republic, there remains little hope for finding decent rented shelter for the Romanian most disadvantaged people (not unlike Hungary). At the marginal rental segment of the market, I found dominant structures of *greed and exploitation*, twined with that of *cruel optimism*: hoping against all odds to receive a social tenancy. Overall, the literature substantiated that the private renting sector can work well for better-off tenants who so are in a less asymmetric socioeconomic relationship with their landlords but fails the poor, even when exceptionally assisted in the Czech Republic. States should focus in transforming the context of cruel optimism to one of optimism regarding the low-income peoples' attachment to secure and affordable social housing just as they do so in relation to middle-income people access to homeownership.

Regarding the affective economies of Ghana and despite state's practice of care in terms of rent control, it was impossible to see anything else than blatant economic, symbolic and physical *exploitation* of renters (including but also beyond the 2-to-5 years advanced rent) paired with relations of *cruel optimism* either for engaging in self-building one's home by the few (with all the

struggle and sacrifices required) or despondently enduring precarious renting for lifetime by the many. This tragic situation in Ghana has been long in the making by economic factors (economic crises, inflation, structural adjustment), state housing policies (retreat from public housing provision), and demographic trends (massive population growth in the country and in urban centers). It will likewise require long term interventions and massive investment in order to be redressed. Meanwhile, people cannot but live and endure (Simone 2013; Simone 2018) while us, as scholars, should militate for global justice.

To be continued and refined.

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